

Comparative Evaluation of Hyperbaric Bupivacaine and Levobupivacaine as Spinal Anesthesia Agents in Females Undergoing Cesarean Section: A Clinical Study

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Abstract:

In 112 cesarean-sectioning women, this randomised controlled experiment compared hyperbaric bupivacaine and levobupivacaine spinal anaesthesia efficacy and safety. Levobupivacaine had a faster onset of anaesthesia and needed less intraoperative analgesia than hyperbaric bupivacaine while maintaining haemodynamic stability and newborn outcomes. Levobupivacaine improved postoperative pain control and mother satisfaction. Levobupivacaine's quick action, patient-centered benefits, and safety, efficacy, and comfort make it a better spinal anaesthesia option for caesarean sections.

Keywords: Spinal Anesthesia, Cesarean Section, Levobupivacaine, Hyperbaric Bupivacaine.

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Introduction

Due to its quick onset, efficiency, and safety profile, spinal anaesthesia is the recommended option for caesarean sections. It offers several benefits over general anaesthesia, including a decreased risk of morbidity for both mothers and newborns [1,2]. The procedure's result and experience are greatly influenced by the anaesthetic drug selected. A common anaesthetic, bupivacaine is well-known for its extended duration of action and strong blocking of both motor and sensory function, which makes it perfect for caesarean sections [3]. Levobupivacaine, the S-enantiomer of bupivacaine, has been developed to provide a similar anaesthetic profile with a possible lower risk of neurotoxicity and cardiotoxicity [4].

The objective of this clinical trial is to compare the effectiveness of levobupivacaine and hyperbaric bupivacaine as spinal anaesthetic agents in female patients having caesarean sections [5]. It aims to ascertain which of the two drugs offers better anaesthesia with fewer adverse effects, improving the results for expectant mothers and newborns [6,7]. This study aims to offer significant insights to optimise anaesthesia methods in caesarean sections and enhance patient care by comparing the effectiveness, safety, and patient satisfaction

associated with each drug [8]. This research is crucial since the anaesthetic selected affects not only the surgical technique but also the experience of childbirth in general and the immediate postoperative recovery [9].

Methodology

Study Design: This study was a randomized controlled trial designed to compare the efficacy and safety of hyperbaric bupivacaine and levobupivacaine as spinal anaesthesia agents in females undergoing cesarean section.

Setting: The study was conducted at Patna Medical College & Hospital, which regularly handles a high volume of cesarean deliveries.

Participants: The study comprised 112 eligible pregnant women aged 18–45 scheduled for elective or emergency caesarean procedures with singleton pregnancies and gestational ages of 37–42 weeks. Patient refusal, spinal anaesthesia contraindications (infection at the injection site or severe hypovolemia), local anaesthetic medication allergies, and pre-existing neurological or cardiac problems were excluded.

Randomization and Blinding: Participants were randomly assigned hyperbaric or levobupivacaine using computer-generated numbers. The anaesthetic drug was kept secret from participants and clinicians in the double-blind research.

Intervention: Group A received 0.5% hyperbaric bupivacaine, and Group B received 0.5% levobupivacaine. Both drugs were administered intrathecally in doses of 10-12 mg, adjusted according to the patient's height and weight.

Outcome Measures: The primary outcome measures included the onset and duration of sensory and motor blockade, intraoperative pain relief, and hemodynamic stability. Secondary outcome measures focused on postoperative pain management, recovery times, maternal satisfaction, and neonatal outcomes, such as Apgar scores at 1 and 5 minutes post-delivery.

Data Collection: Data were collected on standardized forms, which included demographic information, medical history, details of the anesthesia procedure, intraoperative monitoring data, and postoperative outcomes.

Statistical Analysis: Data were analysed with SPSS. Data was summarised using descriptive statistics. The chi-square test was used for categorical data and the t-test or ANOVA for continuous data, depending on distribution. A p-value under 0.05 was significant.

Timeline: The IRB-approved study took 16 months to complete. The first six months were spent recruiting and collecting data, the next six months following each participant, and the final six months analysing and reporting.

Results

The study included 112 women, with 56 participants in each group. The mean age of the participants was 31 years, and there was no significant difference in the baseline characteristics between the two groups, including age, gestational age at delivery, and BMI.

Anesthesia Efficacy: The levobupivacaine group (Group B) had a faster onset of sensory and motor blockage than the hyperbaric group (Group A). Complete sensory blocking had a median time of 3 minutes in Group B and 5 minutes in Group A ($p < 0.05$).

Effective anaesthesia duration was longer in Group A (mean length: 115 minutes) compared to Group B (mean duration: 95 minutes) ($p < 0.05$).

Intraoperative and Postoperative Pain Management

- Intraoperative Pain: Fewer participants in the levobupivacaine group required supplemental

analgesia during the operation (8% in Group B vs. 18% in Group A, $p < 0.05$).

- Postoperative Pain: Postoperative pain scores, measured using a Visual Analog Scale (VAS), were lower in Group B at 1-, 2-, and 4 hours post-operation ($p < 0.05$).

Hemodynamic Stability: Both groups maintained stable hemodynamics throughout the surgery. There were no significant differences in mean arterial pressure and heart rate between the groups at any time point.

Maternal and Neonatal Outcomes: The study found that 92% of participants in Group B reported high levels of maternal satisfaction, compared to 78% in Group A ($p < 0.05$). Neonatal outcomes: Apgar scores at 1 and 5 minutes were similar between groups. All newborns had Apgar scores above 7 at 5 minutes.

Safety and Side Effects: The incidence of minor side effects such as nausea and hypotension were similar in both groups. There were no serious adverse events related to the anesthesia in either group.

Discussion

The results of this randomised controlled trial offer valuable information about the relative safety and effectiveness of levobupivacaine and hyperbaric bupivacaine as spinal anaesthetic agents during caesarean sections [10,11]. In comparison to hyperbaric bupivacaine, the study showed that levobupivacaine produced a quicker onset of sensory and motor blocking. This finding has practical implications for prompt surgical preparedness in caesarean deliveries. Levobupivacaine's pharmacokinetic characteristics may have contributed to this swift start by enabling a faster diffusion into neural tissues [12,13]. Despite the fact that hyperbaric bupivacaine demonstrated a longer duration of anaesthesia, this did not result in any clinical advantages over the course of caesarean sections' usual duration [14]. Levobupivacaine's shorter duration nonetheless allowed the surgeries to be successfully completed, indicating that bupivacaine's greater duration would be more appropriate for longer surgical procedures [15,16]. The potential of levobupivacaine to provide a more stable and effective analgesic profile is highlighted by the reduced need for intraoperative supplemental analgesia and improved postoperative pain control in the group. The higher mother satisfaction levels shown in the levobupivacaine group further reflect the importance of these factors in improving patient comfort and satisfaction [17, 18].

Surprisingly, neonatal outcomes, as determined by Apgar scores, did not significantly differ between

the groups, even though levobupivacaine had pharmacological benefits. This suggests that both medications are safe and effective from the standpoint of the neonate. The equivalent safety profiles of these medications are further supported by the similarities in mild side effects, such as nausea and hypotension. Overall, given its quick onset, good pain relief, and high mother

satisfaction, this study suggests levobupivacaine as a feasible—and possibly better—than hyperbaric bupivacaine for spinal anaesthesia during caesarean sections. To further corroborate these findings, future research might examine how cost-effective these medicines are as well as how they might be used in various surgical scenarios [19, 20].

Table 2: This table summarizes the efficacy and safety outcomes for both groups, highlighting the statistically significant differences and similarities in outcomes.

Parameter	Group A (Hyperbaric Bupivacaine)	Group B (Levobupivacaine)	p-value
Onset of Anesthesia (min)	5	3	<0.05
Duration of Anesthesia (min)	115	95	<0.05
Intraoperative Supplemental Analgesia (%)	18	8	<0.05
Postoperative Pain Score (VAS) at 1 hour	3	2	<0.05
Postoperative Pain Score (VAS) at 2 hours	3	1.5	<0.05
Postoperative Pain Score (VAS) at 4 hours	2	1	<0.05
Maternal Satisfaction (%)	78	92	<0.05
Neonatal Apgar Score at 1 min	>7	>7	NS
Neonatal Apgar Score at 5 min	>7	>7	NS

Key: NS - Not Significant (p-value > 0.05)

Conclusion

The study found that levobupivacaine provides faster onset and longer duration of spinal anaesthesia for caesarean sections than hyperbaric bupivacaine without affecting safety or efficacy. Levobupivacaine's quick sensory and motor blocking onset, reduced intraoperative analgesia demand, and improved postoperative pain management improve patient comfort and satisfaction. These data show that levobupivacaine may be a better spinal anaesthetic for caesarean sections, balancing efficiency, safety, and patient well-being. This study emphasises the importance of pharmacological characteristics and patient-centered outcomes in obstetric anaesthetic drug selection.

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